

FIG. S1. Maximum likelihood tree inferred from ITS DNA sequence data. Bootstrap support percentages ≥ 50 are shown above branches with values from the equivalent parsimony analysis following the slash. An asterisk marks a branch not present in the strict consensus of the eight most parsimonious trees. Scale units are expected number of substitutions per site. Two-letter codes indicate collection localities for ingroup taxa: EB = Europa Bay; EY = El Yunque; GU = Guajataca; LR = La Robleda; MA = Maricao; MH = Minna Hill; SC = La Silla de Calderon; SJ = Saint John; SK = Saint Kitts; TC = Tetas de Cayey. See Appendix 1 for voucher details.

FIG. S2. Maximum likelihood tree inferred from ETS DNA sequence data. Bootstrap support percentages ≥ 50 are shown above branches with values from the equivalent parsimony analysis following the slash. An asterisk marks a branch not present in the strict consensus of the four most parsimonious trees. Scale units are expected number of substitutions per site. Two-letter codes indicate collection localities for ingroup taxa: EB = Europa Bay; EY = El Yunque; GU = Guajataca; LR = La Robleda; MA = Maricao; MH = Minna Hill; SC = La Silla de Calderon; SJ = Saint John; SK = Saint Kitts; TC = Tetas de Cayey. See Appendix 1 for voucher details.

FIG. S3. Maximum likelihood tree inferred from *MeNu79* consensus DNA sequence data. Bootstrap support percentages ≥ 50 are shown above branches with values from the equivalent parsimony analysis following the slash. Asterisks mark branches not present in the strict consensus of the 270 most parsimonious trees. Scale units are expected number of substitutions per site. Two-letter codes indicate collection localities for ingroup taxa: EB = Europa Bay; EY = El Yunque; GU = Guajataca; LR = La Robleda; MA = Maricao; MH = Minna Hill; SC = La Silla de Calderon; SJ = Saint John; SK = Saint Kitts; TC = Tetas de Cayey. See Appendix 1 for voucher details.

FIG. S4. Maximum likelihood tree inferred from *MeNu79* allelic DNA sequence data. Bootstrap support percentages ≥ 50 are shown above branches with values from the equivalent parsimony analysis following the slash. All branches were present in the strict consensus of the three most parsimonious trees. Scale units are expected number of substitutions per site. Two-letter codes indicate collection localities for ingroup taxa: EB = Europa Bay; EY = El Yunque; GU = Guajataca; LR = La Robleda; MA = Maricao; MH = Minna Hill; SC = La Silla de Calderon; SJ = Saint John; SK = Saint Kitts; TC = Tetas de Cayey. See Appendix 1 for voucher details. "A" and "B" distinguish different alleles from heterozygous samples.

FIG. S5. Maximum likelihood tree inferred from cpDNA (concatenated *psbA-trnH* and *ndhF-rpl32*) sequence data. Bootstrap support percentages ≥ 50 are shown above branches with values from the equivalent parsimony analysis following the slash. All branches were present in the strict consensus of the two most parsimonious trees. Scale units are expected number of substitutions per site. Two-letter codes indicate collection localities for ingroup taxa: EB = Europa Bay; EY = El Yunque; GU = Guajataca; LR = La Robleda; MA = Maricao; MH = Minna Hill; SC = La Silla de Calderon; SJ = Saint John; SK = Saint Kitts; TC = Tetras de Cayey. See Appendix 1 for voucher details.